

**DECISION MAKING, PARENTAL ADJUSTMENT AND SENSE OF
RESPONSIBILITY AMONG TEENAGE PARENTS: BASIS IN
THE DEVELOPMENT OF POSTER FOR EARLY
PARENTHOOD PREVENTION TOWARDS
BETTER QUALITY OF LIFE**

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Decision Making, Parental Adjustment and Sense of Responsibility among Teenage Parents: Basis in the Development of Poster for Early Parenthood Prevention Towards Better Quality of Life

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Abstract

The research on teenage parenthood delves deeply into the multifaceted challenges faced by this demographic in contemporary society. This research endeavors to explore the multifaceted decision-making processes, parental adjustments, and evolving sense of responsibility among teenage parents, aiming to poster for early parenthood prevention that enhances the well-being of this demographic. Employing a descriptive phenomenological research approach, this qualitative investigation examines the real-life experiences of ten teenage parents aged 18 to 19 through an online survey. The findings highlight diverse demographic profiles encompassing varying educational backgrounds, marital statuses, and numbers of children among participants. Notably, decision-making skills are influenced by collaborative efforts, partner support, and familial guidance, emphasizing the crucial roles of time management and strategic planning in their lives. Parental adjustment involves significant life transitions and prioritization of family-centeredness. The sense of responsibility among teenage parents varies and is shaped by individual maturity levels and support networks, with parental guidance and personal growth profoundly impacting their sense of accountability. This research yields valuable insights for developing targeted interventions aimed at supporting teenage parents and preventing early parenthood, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of their overall well-being and societal outcomes.

Keywords: *teenage parenthood, decision-making, parental adjustment, sense of responsibility, early parenthood prevention*

Introduction

The evolving world today underscores the importance of understanding how young parents make decisions, adjust to parenthood, and feel responsible. This research delves into the experiences of teenage parents, aiming to gather insights to prevent early parenthood and improve the lives of young parents.

Teenage parenthood presents a complex web of challenges, intertwining decision-making, parental adjustment, and a sense of responsibility. Recent data from the Philippines Statistics Authority (2023) revealed a 5.4% pregnancy rate among individuals aged 15 to 19 in 2022, up from 3.5% in 2017. This surge demands a targeted approach to understand and address the intricacies of early parenthood.

This study examines the dynamics of decision-making, parental adjustment and sense of responsibility among teenage parents, aiming to create a guide to prevent early parenthood. By understanding the influence of parenthood on these aspects, the research seeks to provide a clearer picture of teenage parenthood's complexities.

The study aims to equip teenage parents with tools for informed decision-making and role adaptation, contributing to a strategic framework for preventing early parenthood and improving their quality of life.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of teenage parents concerning age, gender, educational attainment, marital status, and number of children?
2. How do teenage parents make decisions in terms of parenting their children?
3. What are the experienced adjustments of teenage parents?
4. How do teenage parents navigate their sense of responsibility towards their child/children?

Literature Review

Decision-Making Among Teenage Parents

Teenage pregnancy rates have remained high, often attributed to factors such as ignorance about sexuality issues and economic pressures leading some teenagers to engage in sex for financial gain. The decision-making process regarding whether to continue a pregnancy is complex and influenced by various factors, with many teenagers believing that the father should have a significant say in the final decision (Bain et al., 2020). Furthermore, the involvement of the sexual partner significantly impacts women's decision-making and distress levels during this period (Brauer et al., 2019).

Confidence in one's abilities plays a crucial role in decision-making autonomy, with women who possess greater self-confidence more likely to make autonomous choices regarding their pregnancies (Brien et al., 2020). However, risky sexual behaviors, low educational attainment, and a lack of contraception self-efficacy increased the likelihood of future parenthood among male teenagers (Powers et al., 2021).

The transition from teenager to parenthood at a young age often turns into the emotion of regret among teenage parents, who may lament the loss of their previous freedoms and opportunities, such as completing their education (Cariño, 2023).

In summary, decision-making among teenage parents was influenced by a myriad of factors, including socio-economic status, confidence levels, partner involvement, and cultural beliefs. Understanding these factors was essential for developing effective interventions aimed at supporting teenage parents and preventing early parenthood.

Parental Adjustment Among Teenage Parents

The adaptation of teenage parents is vital for the overall well-being of both parents and children following the transition from adolescence to parenthood. Early-pregnancy depression symptoms have been linked to higher paternal adjustment problems and negative attitudes throughout the parenthood transition (Pinto et al., 2020).

Programs focused on guidance and counseling have demonstrated notable benefits in enhancing teenage mothers' intellectual, emotional, mental, and social adjustment, resulting in improved outcomes for both mothers and their children. (Opondo et al., 2020).

Adolescent fathers' engagement is essential for the psychological development of the child, with positive interactions and resources such as parenting workshops playing a vital role in fostering a strong father-child bond (Powers et al., 2021).

Teenage fathers have often experienced a shift from financial dependence on their parents to the responsibility of providing for their children, which has led to unspoken feelings of unpreparedness and stress. However, many teenage fathers expressed a commitment to fulfill their paternal role and appreciate the support provided by their parents during this transition (Cariño, 2023).

According to Raising Children Network (2023), teenage parenthood poses unique challenges for mothers and fathers, including balancing school completion and societal judgment. However, when parents provide a foundation of reliability, love, and support, children thrive in their growth and development.

Despite the joy of becoming parents, teenage mothers often have to face emotional struggles, including self-doubt, guilt, and isolation, due to societal pressure and lack of experience (Sanders et al., 2021).

Adolescent mothers found sustainable wellness for their newborns challenging due to a lack of knowledge and conflicting advice, but dedication to their infant's well-being and social support are crucial factors in maternal competence (Erfina et al., 2019). However, the adjustment process was not without its difficulties, as some teenage parents face disapproval and rejection from their families, which leads to psychological instability and financial hardships (Govender et al., 2020).

In summary, parental adjustment among teenage parents involves various emotional, social, and practical challenges, highlighting the significance of support programs and resources to facilitate a smooth transition to parenthood and enhance the well-being of both parents and children.

Sense of Responsibility Among Teenage Parents

The sense of responsibility among teenage parents was a critical aspect of their journey into parenthood. Young women and men frequently contemplate their reproductive options and consider different motherhood scenarios while making educational and career plans, demonstrating a proactive approach toward family planning and financial stability (Bodin et al., 2021).

Teenage fathers also demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility toward their children, prioritizing their needs over their own and adjusting their lifestyles accordingly. Despite facing challenges such as self-regulation and feeling overwhelmed, teenage parents understand they recognize the gravity of their responsibilities and strive to meet the needs of their children (Cariño, 2023).

According to TACAdmin (2022), when confronted with unexpected pregnancies, teenage parents assess their readiness for parenthood, seek advice from trusted sources, and reflect on the challenges associated with teenage parenting.

However, teenage fathers have often grappled with conflicting expectations of adult masculinity and youthful freedom, which has made it challenging for them to fully embrace their father roles (Weber, 2020).

In summary, teenage parents' sense of responsibility encompasses a complex interplay of family planning, emotional maturity, and societal expectations. Understanding these dynamics was essential for developing effective interventions to support teenage parents and promote positive outcomes for both parents and children.

Collaborative Consideration for Child-Centered Decision-Making

Collaborative Decision-Making

In the study by the Helfand (2024), decision-making is described as more than just making a choice; it involves identifying what needs to be done, determining how to achieve it, and reflecting on motivations and consequences.

Teenagers exercise prudent and logical decision-making skills, driven by our concern for their safety. Effective communication with teenagers significantly influences their receptivity to guidance. Effective communication fosters acceptance of our teachings, while ineffective communication can lead to resistance.

Ginsburg (2024) highlighted that teens strive to make the right decisions and value adult guidance in navigating their choices. Similarly, SmithBattle et al. (2019) emphasize the importance of building trusting and collaborative relationships with teenage parents, which is crucial for helping them tailor their care to fit their personal and family circumstances. According to the Helfand (2024), decision-making affects everyday life, and these skills are learned over time from the people around us. Teenagers, especially those who initially act on impulse, need adult guidance to develop healthy decision-making habits.

Consideration of Child's Well-being

In the successful transition to motherhood among adolescents, various factors come into play, including physical challenges associated with childbirth and breastfeeding, psychological health, competence in infant care, social backing, educational and financial pressures, and access to healthcare services. Existing literature suggests a correlation between social support networks and the cultivation of a favorable maternal identity during the transition phase into adolescent motherhood.

A study by Erfina et al. (2019) found that adolescent mothers experience an increased burden of responsibility during the transition to motherhood, reflecting the challenges. That is why a study by Zhang (2022) highlights the critical role of grandparental support in assisting teenage parents, particularly in managing childcare responsibilities and decision-making.

Furthermore, According to Li et al. (2024), parental self-regulation is believed to significantly impact teenage adjustment. By utilizing the intergenerational transmission model of self-regulation, we investigated the notion that parental self-control fosters adolescent well-being by reducing parental stress and promoting mindful parenting, consequently enhancing adolescent self-control. Additionally, the study by Williamson-Garner (2019) observed that teenage parents often prioritize their children's needs over their own, indicative of their commitment to their child's well-being despite their young age. By supporting this study, there is also another study that focuses on respect and improving communication skills in parenting. Families can build an atmosphere where every conversation helps strengthen their bonds (Richard, 2023).

Adaptive Decision-Making

According to the PEM Confinement Nanny Agency website (2022), parenthood is undoubtedly challenging and can be quite difficult. As one embarks on their journey as a new parent, everything feels unfamiliar, and they are likely to experience a range of mixed emotions. That is why the study of Govender et al. (2020) explains that the added responsibilities of parenthood significantly influence teenagers' decision-making processes, highlighting how these young parents adapt their behaviors to meet their new roles and responsibilities.

Adaptation and Growth in Parenthood

Emotional Well-being

Parental welfare affects not only the parents but also the development of the child, which makes parental well-being essential (Nomaguchi & Milkie, 2020).

The necessity of carving out moments of solitude for parents suggests that even brief periods of alone time can significantly aid in recharging and maintaining emotional health. This practice is essential for teenage parents who must navigate the complexities of their roles while still finding time for self-care (Morin, 2020). In the study of Hennepin Healthcare (2023), it stated that teen mothers are more likely than other teenage women to suffer from post-traumatic stress disorder, and many may have experienced abuse or trauma in the past. It's crucial to remind teenage parents that they're not alone. There is support available to assist individuals who are caring for a teenager, and it's important to be knowledgeable about how people can be of help, especially since the Texas Adoption Center (2020) stated that not every adolescent mother has the support of her family and friends. This shift in their support system may leave teen mothers feeling isolated in a difficult circumstance, with little compassion or direction.

Coping Strategies

Detecting stress-stricken teenagers could open avenues for tailored clinical preventive interventions. Nonetheless, resilience evaluations are seldom conducted within clinical contexts, and there is a lack of clear, evidence-supported protocols or frameworks for such assessments. The study by Phillips (2019) found that participants manage stress through self-reliant activities and distraction techniques, indicating a common reliance on personal resilience strategies to handle stress.

Familial bonds exert a substantial influence on mental and emotional well-being. Engaging in activities in meaningful conversations can alleviate stress and foster feelings of happiness and fulfillment. Uniyal (2023) supports this view, highlighting that spending quality time with family can significantly enhance overall well-being.

According to Adangabe et al. (2021), successful coping often involves direct problem-solving and cognitive restructuring. Effective coping entails proactive problem-solving, cognitive analysis, seeking knowledge, and restructuring one's thoughts. Each of these strategies aims to address stressors by managing them either intellectually or behaviorally. The study by Wolf et al. (2021) suggested that parents who drink alcohol may require additional support to manage stress and avoid negative impacts on their parenting. Fleming (2023) stated that if a father fails to address his setbacks, he may have physical health issues, develop an alcohol or drug addiction, and struggle with elevated stress levels.

Balancing Life as an Individual and a Parent

The difficulties faced by teenage parents in balancing parenthood. A common problem for teenagers is not having enough time to handle their many roles, causing extra stress and difficulty in managing both being a parent and studying (Salino, 2023). Meanwhile, the research studies by Lada-Masko and Kazmierczak (2021) discuss the importance of placing parenthood within one's value system and understanding the motives behind parental actions.

Comprehensive Commitment to Child's Well-being and Long-Term Development

Prioritizing Children's Welfare

According to the Jai Institute for Parenting (2024), numerous studies corroborate the idea that our past experiences significantly shape our parenting styles, and childhood trauma can exert a far-reaching influence on parenting. That is why a new study by Adetunji (2024) demonstrated that parents who exhibit empathy towards their children may facilitate the early development of this trait in their adolescents. Furthermore, adolescents who demonstrate empathy and provide support to their peers are more likely to transition into nurturing parents, thereby potentially fostering empathy in their future offspring. Aside from that, the study shown by López-Martínez (2019) indicates that positive and open communication in families helps to develop self-esteem and emotional well-being. Li and Guo (2023) discovered that the presence of parents significantly influences children's well-being. Their research highlights the importance of increasing the time parents spend with their children and recognizing the unique needs of each child.

Reflecting on Long-Term Impact

The study of Shehandlesit (2023) states that the role of a parent is lifelong, and it's essential to embrace it fully by being present and supportive while encouraging independence. A supporting study by Gibson (2021) emphasizes that parenthood is always a work in process, with parents continually needing to consider important aspects of raising children.

Also, in the study of Rohmalimna et al. (2022), we have to consider that parental parenting is an interaction and action between parents and their children that lasts until the child develops into an adult.

Parental Roles

According to the Australian Parenting Website (2023), as a teenage parent, what truly counts is their actions. When parents provide consistent, affectionate, caring, supportive, attentive, and adaptable parenting, children thrive. However, teenage parents often encounter additional obstacles as they navigate parenthood. Based on the website of Psychology Today (2024), parents might increase their criticism or questioning towards their children compared to earlier and become more vigilant, cautious, and stringent in their approach. However, for Scott (2023), this situation can lead to downward social comparison, in a way that we sometimes compare ourselves to others whom we perceive as being in a less fortunate situation than us, hoping to find solace in our own circumstances. Though it may seem unkind, this behavior is something almost everyone has experienced at some point. From that, we can say that being a teenage parent is hard in a way they experience managing their roles as complex and challenging (Espiritu et al., 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive phenomenological research design and qualitative approach to investigate Decision Making, Parental Adjustment, and Sense of Responsibility among Teenage Parents. According to Neubauer et al. (2019), phenomenology in qualitative research focuses on exploring individuals' direct experiences within their lived contexts. Researchers in phenomenology document and analyze the thoughts, emotions, and perspectives of the participants, while maintaining awareness of the researcher's own assumptions and viewpoints being irrelevant to the study (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). Initially planning in-depth interviews, the study adapted to using an open-ended questionnaire to gather data, which was subsequently analyzed. This approach enabled the researchers to collect valuable insights that informed the development of an early parenthood prevention poster, aimed at improving the quality of life for teenage parents.

Participants

The demographic profile of the respondents, chosen using the purposive sampling method, indicates an equal distribution of teenage parents between the ages of 16-17 and 18-19, with each age group comprising 50% of the sample. Gender representation is also balanced, with 50% female and 50% male respondents. In terms of educational attainment, half of the respondents hold an associate

degree, 40% have some college education, and 10% are high school graduates. Marital status shows that 60% of the respondents are single, 30% are married, and 10% are separated. Regarding the number of children, the majority (80%) have 1-2 children, while 20% have 3-4 children.

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents*

	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Age (when they had their first baby)	16-17	5
	18-19	5
	Total	10
Gender	Female	5
	Male	5
	Total	10
Educational Attainment	High School Graduate	1
	Some College	4
	Associate Degree	5
	Total	10
Marital Status	Single	6
	Married	3
	Separated	1
	Total	10
Number of Children	1-2	8
	3-4	2
	Total	10

Instrument

Data collection employed an online survey tool via Google Forms, leveraging the benefits highlighted by Salvatori (2023), such as increased response rates, cost-effectiveness, and real-time access to results. The survey, administered to ten participants aged eighteen (18) and nineteen (19) who became parents during their early teenage years, consisted of a validated open-ended questionnaire with ten (10) categorized questions: decision-making, parental adjustment, and sense of responsibility. This qualitative approach aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of teenage parenthood challenges, informing the poster's development and offering diverse perspectives on the experiences of teenage parents.

Procedure

To explore decision making, parental adjustment, and sense of responsibility among teenage parents and develop an early parenthood prevention poster, this study utilized two data sources: primary data obtained through a validated open-ended questionnaire with ten (10) questions and secondary data from journals, books, and relevant articles. Data collection involved purposive sampling of ten (10) teenage parents aged eighteen (18) and nineteen (19), specifically those who became parents during their early teenage years. The questionnaire was administered online via Google Forms to ensure ethical standards, respondent security, and adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Post-survey, Colaizzi's Method was employed for data analysis, involving transcription, extraction of significant statements, formulation of meanings, clustering of themes, and validation of findings through participant confirmation. This qualitative approach provided comprehensive insights into teenage parenthood experiences while developing practical solutions through a systematic research process.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of St. Dominic College of Asia based on the compliance with the minimum standards of the SDCA Research Guidelines. Respondents were deployed based on their willingness to participate in this study with informed consent.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. *Summary of Emergent Themes and Subordinate Themes*

<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Decision Making: Collaborative Consideration for Child-Centered Decision-Making	Collaborative Decision-Making Consideration of Child's Well-being Adaptive Decision-Making
Parental Adjustment: Adaptation and Growth in Parenthood	Emotional Well-being Coping Strategies Balancing Life as an Individual and a Parent
Sense of Responsibility: Comprehensive Commitment to Child's Well-being and Long-Term Development	Prioritizing Child's Welfare Reflecting on Long-Term Impact Parental Roles

The table summarizes findings from a study using Colaizzi's method with 10 respondents from Cavite. Three key themes emerged: collaborative decision-making focused on children's well-being, parental adjustment involving emotional well-being and coping, and a strong sense of responsibility prioritizing the child's welfare and long-term development.

Upon analysis of the participants' responses, the theme of collaborative consideration for child-centered decision-making emerged. Under this emergent theme, the participants' answers were classified into different subthemes: collaborative decision-making, consideration of the child's well-being, and adaptive decision-making.

Collaborative decision-making involves individuals seeking advice and input from older family members, spouses, and broader familial networks to make informed decisions, especially concerning their children. This approach emphasizes planning and consideration before taking action, reflecting a shift in decision-making dynamics after becoming parents. Respect and mutual understanding within partnerships are key, with final decisions often involving mutual agreement or respect for each other's perspectives.

Consideration of Child's Well-being focuses on how teenage parents prioritize decisions that impact their children's welfare. They often feel the weight of responsibility, especially in health-related decisions, navigating challenges while prioritizing their child's needs. External guidance from family, particularly grandparents, plays a crucial role in supporting these young parents in their decision-making process.

Adaptive Decision-Making highlights how teenage parents adjust their decision-making processes to accommodate the responsibilities of parenthood. This adaptation involves significant lifestyle changes and a shift from self-centered decision-making to a more thoughtful, child-centric approach. It reflects their evolving roles and responsibilities as they navigate the complexities of parenting at a young age.

The analysis of the respondents' answers revealed the theme of adapting and growing in parenthood. Under this emergent theme, the participants' answer was classified into different subthemes: emotional well-being, coping strategies, and Balancing Life as an Individual and a Parent.

Emotional Well-being explores how teenage parents prioritize maintaining their emotional health amidst the challenges of parenthood. Participants emphasize the importance of balancing personal time with parental responsibilities to ensure well-being. Strategies include recognizing personal limits and carving out moments for solitude, which are crucial for recharge. This approach aligns with research suggesting that brief periods of self-care significantly contribute to emotional resilience among parents.

Coping Strategies focuses on the diverse methods teenage parents use to manage the stresses of parenting. Strategies range from emotional release and distraction techniques to proactive approaches like enjoying family time and problem-solving through communication. However, some participants resort to less healthy coping mechanisms, such as substance use, highlighting the need for support and intervention. Research underscores the importance of effective coping strategies in mitigating stress and enhancing overall well-being among young parents.

Balancing Life as an Individual and a Parent addresses the dual challenges teenage parents face in managing their personal lives alongside their parental responsibilities. Participants stress the importance of finding personal time amidst caregiving duties, often navigating logistical challenges with support from family and external help. This subtheme underscores the complexity of balancing multiple roles and responsibilities, emphasizing the value of personal commitment and support systems in sustaining parental roles effectively.

The theme of Comprehensive Commitment to Children's Well-being and Long-Term Development emerged from the analysis of the respondents' answers. Under this emergent theme, the participants' answer was classified into different subthemes: prioritizing child's-welfare, reflecting on long term impact, and balancing personal and parental roles.

Prioritizing Child's Welfare explores how teenage parents strive to break negative parenting cycles from their own upbringing and adopt positive approaches. Participants emphasize open communication, emotional support, and fostering a nurturing environment to meet their child's emotional and physical needs. Research underscores the lasting impact of childhood experiences on parenting styles and the importance of positive interactions in shaping children's well-being.

Reflecting on Long-Term Impact focuses on participants' reflections about the lifelong commitment of parenthood. They express dedication to supporting their children through all stages of life, fostering independence while providing unwavering support. This theme highlights the ongoing nature of parenting and the need for parents to adapt their roles as their children grow and develop.

Parental Roles examines the challenges teenage parents face in managing their roles and responsibilities. Participants navigate the complexities of balancing personal aspirations with the demands of parenthood, often undergoing significant lifestyle adjustments. Research underscores the mixed messages and anxieties parents face about making the "right" choices while highlighting the complexities and challenges inherent in teenage parenthood.

Emergent Theme 1: Collaborative Consideration for Child-Centered Decision Making

Bronfenbrenner's Socio-Ecological System theory underscores the influence of environmental systems on individual decisions. In

collaborative decision-making among teenage parents, the mesosystem—interactions within their immediate support network, like family and close relationships—plays a pivotal role. This theory clarifies how these parents rely on their support network for guidance, shaping decisions that prioritize their children's well-being.

Collaborative Decision-Making

Decision-Making encompasses beyond mere selection, emphasizing the processes of recognizing tasks, devising strategies for attainment, and contemplating motivations and repercussions (Helfand, 2024). Participants highlighted the importance of seeking advice from older family members to make informed decisions for their children, underscoring the collaborative nature of their decision-making processes. This reliance on familial advice reflects a broader pattern observed in family decision-making dynamics (Ginsburg, 2024; SmithBattle et al., 2019). For instance, Ginsburg (2024) notes that teens value adult guidance in navigating choices effectively, aligning with the participants' reliance on parental wisdom. SmithBattle et al. (2019) emphasize the significance of building trusting relationships with teenage parents to tailor care effectively to family circumstances, a principle mirrored in the participants' interactions with their partners and extended family.

The involvement of spouses in decision-making was also highlighted, with participants emphasizing joint decision-making processes and respectful communication within partnerships. This collaborative approach, where decisions are discussed and respected within familial and spousal contexts, echoes findings that emphasize respect and effective communication as crucial components of parenting dynamics (Richard, 2023).

Consideration of Child's Well-being

Teenage parents underscore the weight of responsibility in making decisions impacting their children's well-being. For instance, challenges in making health-related decisions were highlighted, reflecting the significant burden felt during the early years of parenting (Erfina et al., 2019). Williamson-Garner (2019) notes that teenage parents often prioritize their children's needs over their own, demonstrating a commitment to their child's well-being despite their young age. External guidance, particularly from grandparents, plays a crucial role in supporting teenage parents in managing childcare responsibilities and decision-making processes (Zhang, 2022).

The study by Mukherjee (2024) supports these findings, emphasizing parental prioritization of their child's welfare, including considerations for happiness, safety, and overall well-being.

Adaptive Decision-Making

The adaptation of decision-making processes to the new responsibilities of parenthood was a prominent theme. Participants described significant lifestyle changes brought about by parenthood, reflecting a shift from self-centered decision-making to a more thoughtful and considerate approach, with a focus on the potential impact on their children (Govender et al., 2020).

Govender et al. (2020) explain that the added responsibilities of parenthood significantly influence teenagers' decision-making processes, highlighting how these young parents adapt their behaviors to meet their new roles and responsibilities. This adaptation is evident in participants' narratives, where they discuss adjusting their decision-making strategies to prioritize the well-being and needs of their children.

Emergent Theme 2: Adaptation and Growth in Parenthood

Erik Erikson's Psychosocial Development Theory offers a framework for understanding how individuals navigate life's challenges. For teenage parents, stages like 'Identity vs. Role Confusion' and 'Intimacy vs. Isolation' are crucial. These stages highlight the development of a stable identity and forming intimate relationships amidst the responsibilities of parenthood. Parental adjustment involves adapting to new roles, balancing personal growth with parenting demands, and focusing on emotional well-being and effective coping strategies.

Emotional Well-being

In a study by Nomaguchi and Milkie (2020), parental well-being is emphasized as crucial not only for the parents themselves but also for child development, underscoring the significance of managing emotional health. Participants highlighted the importance of balancing personal time with parental responsibilities to maintain emotional well-being. This practice aligns with findings by Morin (2020), who suggests that carving out moments of solitude can significantly aid parents in recharging and managing stress effectively.

Coping Strategies

Teenage parents employ various coping strategies to manage the stresses of parenthood. Research by Phillips (2019) indicates that these strategies often include self-reliant activities and distraction techniques, reflecting a common reliance on personal resilience to handle stress. Spending quality time with family emerged as a vital coping mechanism among participants, supported by Uniyal (2023), who asserts that family interactions contribute significantly to overall well-being.

Additionally, effective coping strategies such as problem-solving and direct communication were noted, echoing findings by Adangabe et al. (2021), which emphasize the role of proactive approaches in stress management. However, less healthy coping mechanisms, like substance use, were also reported among some participants. Research by Mohammed Arshadh and Tengku (2020) highlights substance

abuse as a maladaptive coping strategy among teenagers facing the challenges of early parenthood, necessitating targeted interventions and support.

Balancing Life as an Individual and a Parent

Balancing various life aspects poses a significant challenge for teenage parents, who must navigate multiple roles simultaneously. This challenge is underscored by Salino (2023), who discusses the difficulties in managing parenthood alongside other responsibilities such as education and personal growth. Finding moments of solitude remains crucial, as recommended by Morin (2020), to recharge and maintain individual well-being amidst the demands of parenthood.

Participants' commitment to fulfilling parental responsibilities reflects an alignment with the values discussed by Lada-Masko and Kazmierczak (2021), emphasizing the importance of integrating parenthood into one's value system and understanding the motives behind parental actions.

Emergent Theme 3: Comprehensive Commitment to Child's Well-being and Long-Term Development

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory highlights how parents' behaviors, through observational learning and modeling, strongly impact their children's development. For teenage parents, this theory underscores the critical role of responsibility in shaping their child's future. It emphasizes their commitment to nurturing a supportive environment that promotes their child's well-being and long-term development.

Prioritizing Child's Welfare

Participants expressed a strong commitment to prioritizing their child's welfare, often reflecting on their own upbringing to break negative cycles. Research from the Jai Institute for Parenting (2024) underscores that past experiences significantly shape parenting styles, with childhood trauma influencing parental approaches. Positive communication within families, as emphasized by López-Martínez (2019), fosters emotional well-being and strengthens parent-child relationships. Additionally, providing consistent emotional and physical support, as highlighted by Li and Guo (2023), contributes significantly to children's overall well-being.

Reflecting on Long-Term Impact

Participants reflected on the enduring impact of their parenting decisions, emphasizing a lifelong commitment to their children. Shehandlesit (2023) discusses parenthood as a continuous journey requiring presence, support, and encouragement of independence. Gibson (2021) notes that parenting involves ongoing adaptation and consideration of children's evolving needs. Supporting children in developing independence, as articulated by Participant 6, aligns with Rohmalimna et al. (2022), who emphasize the dynamic interaction between parents and children throughout their growth into adulthood.

Parental Roles

Navigating parental roles presents a significant challenge for teenage parents. Bean (2024) discusses the pervasive influence of societal norms and media on parental expectations, contributing to parental anxiety and uncertainty. Research by Espiritu et al. (2023) acknowledges the complexities faced by teenage parents in managing multiple roles, highlighting the need for support and guidance in fulfilling parental responsibilities effectively.

Conclusions

This study explored the lives of teenage parents, focusing on their decision-making processes, adjustments to parenthood, and sense of responsibility. The research aimed to develop an Early Parenthood Prevention Poster to enhance the well-being of teenage parents. Demographically, the study found an equal distribution of teenage parents aged 16-17 and 18-19, with a balanced gender representation. Educational attainment varied, predominantly with some college education or an associate degree. Most were single, and the majority had 1-2 children.

Teenage parents exhibited a strong commitment to their children's welfare, guided by familial support in decision-making. They transitioned from self-centered to child-centered decision-making, reflecting their deepening dedication to their children's development. Adjusting to parenthood involved balancing personal growth with parental responsibilities, demonstrating resilience and adaptability. Their profound sense of responsibility prioritized their children's well-being, nurturing emotional bonds and collaborative relationships within their families.

In response to these findings, the Early Parenthood Prevention Poster was developed to address the specific challenges faced by teenage parents. Grounded in themes of collaborative and adaptive decision-making, as well as a comprehensive commitment to child well-being, the poster aims to empower teenage parents and foster positive outcomes for both parents and children.

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